

TABLE 1—SURFACE TENSION (σ), VOLUME (V), RIGID SPHERE DIAMETER (d), EXCESS INTERNAL PRESSURE (P_i^E) AND EXCESS FREE LENGTH (L_f^E) FOR THE MIXTURES OF HEXANE (X_1), DECANE (X_2) AND HEXADECANE (X_3) AT 303.15 K

x_1	x_2	σ dyne cm ⁻¹	V cm ³ mol ⁻¹	d Å	P_i^E K bar		L_f^E Å
					Theor.	Exptl.	
0.000 0	0.949 1	23.16	201.944	6.854 0	-0.029 7	-0.029 1	-0.002 8
0.000 0	0.825 6	23.82	214.098	7.022 2	-0.027 3	-0.046 5	-0.008 0
0.000 0	0.734 6	24.18	223.074	7.191 3	-0.026 3	-0.015 5	-0.010 2
0.000 0	0.598 8	24.79	236.429	7.310 2	-0.020 7	-0.019 9	-0.012 1
0.142 0	0.858 0	22.28	187.778	6.739 6	+0.075 2	-0.012 3	-0.010 3
0.142 0	0.753 2	22.44	198.104	6.791 5	+0.047 8	-0.021 7	-0.017 8
0.142 0	0.597 5	23.06	213.433	6.998 7	-0.045 1	-0.034 2	-0.025 2
0.142 0	0.446 7	23.24	228.279	7.178 1	-0.056 8	-0.043 7	-0.029 1
0.267 1	0.732 9	21.68	179.716	6.535 8	-0.025 6	-0.024 0	-0.017 6
0.267 1	0.635 3	21.84	182.337	6.667 6	-0.041 2	-0.028 8	-0.026 5
0.267 1	0.479 5	21.99	204.671	6.865 7	-0.063 1	-0.044 6	-0.036 9
0.267 1	0.390 2	22.16	213.464	6.972 2	-0.075 2	-0.052 7	-0.040 8
0.267 1	0.325 2	22.24	219.871	7.055 9	-0.075 1	-0.038 1	-0.042 7
0.503 1	0.496 9	20.44	164.517	6.300 3	-0.019 7	-0.020 8	-0.024 9
0.503 1	0.378 4	20.38	176.192	6.460 2	-0.053 6	-0.037 5	-0.041 2
0.503 1	0.305 8	20.33	183.338	6.554 0	-0.071 6	-0.047 4	-0.049 1
0.503 1	0.154 7	20.25	194.217	6.741 9	-0.102 1	-0.066 4	-0.061 7
0.503 1	0.098 0	20.27	203.807	6.811 6	-0.110 0	-0.073 0	-0.064 6
0.600 2	0.399 8	19.98	158.252	6.201 1	-0.013 2	-0.019 4	-0.025 1
0.600 2	0.276 1	19.80	170.437	6.361 3	-0.062 8	-0.037 9	-0.045 1
0.600 2	0.189 5	19.66	178.976	6.479 3	-0.081 6	-0.050 3	-0.055 8
0.600 2	0.119 0	19.53	185.921	6.586 1	-0.101 0	-0.060 1	-0.063 1
0.600 2	0.069 8	19.35	190.761	6.622 6	-0.115 8	-0.066 7	-0.067 7

decrease in mole fraction of decane and the increase in mole fraction of hexane.

Hence, from the above discussion, it may be concluded that the theory employed to evaluate excess internal pressure and excess free length for binary liquid mixtures may be successfully extended to ternary liquid mixtures, and P_i^E and L_f^E , like binary liquid mixtures, vary with composition of the mixture in ternary liquid mixture.

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Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of Spiro-[2-isoxazoline-4,2'-(1'H)-naphthalen-1-ones]

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NAPHTHISOXAZOLES are known to exhibit a wide spectrum of physiological properties like analgesic, antipyretic and antiinflammatory activities¹. Recently, the compounds have been reported to possess high antimicrobial activity². The present investigation was taken up with a view to synthesise new derivatives and to screen them for their antimicrobial activity.

2-Benzal-1-tetralones³ obtained by the base-catalysed condensation of 1-tetralone with various aromatic aldehydes have been treated with benzoni-trile oxide in refluxing ether. The nitrile oxide has been generated *in situ* by the action of triethylamine on benzhydroxamoyl chloride⁴. The cyclised

product has been identified as 3,5-diphenyl-3',4'-dihydro-spiro-[2-isoxazoline-4,2'(1'H)-naphthalen-1-one] (3a) on the basis of analytical and spectral data. The addition⁵ of acetonitrile oxide to 2-benzal-1-tetralone also led to the analogous product (3b) (Scheme 1). The reaction with all

Scheme 1

the substituted-benzaltetralones (*p*-methyl, *p*-methoxy, *p*-chloro, *o*-chloro, *p*-nitro) has not given any product, the starting compound being recovered. The reason for non-formation of the products is not clear. The ir spectra showed absorption at 1615 cm^{-1} (C=N), and the convincing proof in favour of the structure of 3a comes from the pmr spectra which showed three multiplets in the high field region in addition to a one-proton singlet at δ 5.5 due to the lone isoxazoline ring proton. The irregular multiplet centered at δ 1.85 comes from the two diastereotopic hydrogens H_b and H_c, whose chemical shift differences are not much as shown by the marked overlap of the peaks. The two benzylic protons H_d and H_e around δ 2.8 and 3.25 as complex multiples indicate their conspicuous non-equivalence. The marked non-equivalence of the two hydrogens may presumably be due to the preferential shielding of a particular proton by a benzene ring. The hydrogen not affected by the ring current is resonating at δ 3.25. All the four hydrogens have *vicinal* as well as *geminal* coupling and hence the complex pattern of the signals. The aromatic protons appeared in the region δ 7.0–8.1.

Mass spectral data of 3a supports the structural assignment (Scheme 2). One of the important fragmentations of the molecular ion is the cycloreversion leading to the ions corresponding to nitrile oxide and benzal tetralone at m/z 119 and 234, respectively. The base peak of the spectrum is at m/z 93 due to the phenoxide formed by the expulsion of CN from benzonitrile oxide fragment. The spectrum shows a metastable peak at m/z 299.2 accounting for the loss of CO from the M^+ giving C at m/z 325. Latter breaks up further leading styrene and isoxazole fragments which appear at m/z 104 and 221, respectively. The expulsion of phenyl ethylene oxide from the isoxazole giving the benzonitrile ion is confirmed by the metastable peak at m/z 48.1. This is in keeping with the well known mass spectral behaviour of isoxazoles⁶. The third metastable peak in the mass spectrum at m/z 293.7 accounts for the loss of HNO from the oxime(G) leading to the spiro-cyclopropene at m/z 322. Similar mass spectral fragmentation was observed for 3b, which showed molecular ion peak at m/z 291.

Experimental

Melting points are uncorrected. The purity of the compounds was checked by tlc. The ir spectra were run on a Perkin-Elmer 577 as KBr disc, 90 MHz pmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 spectrometer using TMS as internal reference, and the mass spectra on a Varian MCH-7 instrument at 70 eV.

3,5-Diphenyl-3',4'-dihydro-spiro[2-isoxazoline-4,2'(1'H)-naphthalen-1-one] (3a): 2-Benzal-1-tetralone (0.01 mol), chloroxime (0.01 mol) and triethylamine (0.01 mol) were refluxed in dry ether for 3–4 h. Separated triethylamine hydrochloride was removed by filtration. Evaporation of the solvent followed by trituration with methanol gave the product

Scheme 2

which was recrystallised from petroleum ether—benzene, (60%), m.p. 182° (Found: C, 81.41; H, 5.40; N, 3.97. $C_{24}H_{19}NO_2$ requires: C, 81.58; H, 5.38; N, 3.96%).

3-Methyl-5-phenyl-3',4'-dihydro-spiro[2-isoxazoline-4,2'-(1'H)-naphthalen-1-one](3b): 2-Benzal-1-tetralone (0.01 mol), nitroethane (0.01 ml) and phenyl isocyanate (0.02 mol) were taken in dry benzene. The solution was cooled in an ice-water bath and stirred while few drops of triethylamine in benzene were added dropwise during 10 min. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 h while stirring. Separated diphenyl urea was removed by filtration. The filtrate was washed with water repeatedly and dried. The product was recrystallised from benzene, (40%), m.p. 196° (Found: C, 78.29; H, 5.81; N, 4.78. $C_{19}H_{17}NO_2$ requires: C, 78.35; H, 5.84; N, 4.81%).

Antibacterial activity: Antibacterial activity was assayed by employing Vincent and Vincent⁷ agar-disc method. All the bacteria employed, both the gram-positive (*Bacillus purnilis*, *Bacillus polymixa* and *Streptococcus albus*) and gram-negative (*Acetobacter acerogenes*, *Proteus vulgaris* and *Pseudomonas ovalis*) were found to be moderately sensitive to the compounds under investigation.

Antifungal activity: The fungicidal activity was studied by glass slide-humid chamber technique⁸ against four phytopathogenic fungi (*Fusarium oxysporum* Schl., *Curvularia lunata* (Walker) Boed., *Drechslera rostrata* and *Alternaria alternata*). The compounds exhibited strong fungicidal activity against all the four organisms and caused total inhibition at 200 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ concentration. The log ED_{50} values for *F. oxysporum*, *C. lunata*, *D. rostrata* and *A. alternata* were 2.1, 2.2, 2.06 and 2.08, respectively.

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3,3'-Di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside from Stem Bark of *Diospyros discolor* Willd.

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THE plant *Diospyros discolor* (syn. *D. mabola*) is a medicinal plant, employed in the indigenous system of medicine^{1,2}. The previous study on the stem bark of *D. discolor* disclosed the presence of a new anthraquinone glycoside³ and a tannin⁴. Our further examination on the stem bark of this plant has now revealed the presence of a new glycoside 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O- β -D-galactopyranosyl-(1 \rightarrow 4)- β -D-glucopyranoside (1), characterised by spectral and chemical analyses.

The glycoside (1), m.p. 220–22° d, gave a yellow colour with alkali, a dark bluish green precipitate with FeCl_3 ⁵, and positive Greissmeyer's reaction⁶, suggesting that it to be an ellagic acid derivative⁵. Its ir (KBr) spectral bands at 3 440–3 410 (br, OH), 1 730 and 1 720 (lactone), 2 870 and 1 175 (methoxyl), 1 590, 1 560 and 1 470 (aromatic) and 820 cm^{-1} (glycoside), and uv (EtOH) characteristic bands at 249, 355 (sh) and 370 nm substantiated this assumption^{7–10}.

Acid hydrolysis of the glycoside gave an aglycone (2) and a mixture of sugars identified as D-galactose and D-glucose by direct comparison with authentic samples (co-pc); 2, m.p. 273–74°, $C_{16}H_{10}O_8$, λ_{max} (EtOH) 248, 359 (sh) and 372 nm analysed for two methoxyl groups (Zeisel's). Its uv spectra exhibited a bathochromic shift of 33 nm in presence of sodium ethylate but no bathochromic shift was discernible with sodium acetate indicating that the aglycone is 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic acid (2), which was confirmed by direct comparison (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁷.

The glycoside on methylation with diazomethane and subsequent acid hydrolysis yielded 3,3',4'-tri-O-methylellagic acid, m.p. 287–88° (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴ which gave a monoacetate, m.p. 260–62° (m.m.p. and co-tlc)⁴. This observation confirmed that both the sugar units are linked at position-4 of the aglycone in the form of a disaccharide. The partial acid hydrolysis of the glycoside yielded D-galactose (co-pc) and 3,3'-di-O-methylellagic-acid-4-O-glucoside, m.p. 213–15°⁸. This is borne out by the fact that D-Galactose was thus proved to be the terminal sugar in 1.

The structure was finally established by permethylation (Hakomori's method)^{11,12} of the glycoside followed by acid hydrolysis which gave 2,3,4,6-tetra-O-methyl-D-galactose, 2,3,6-tri-O-methyl-D-glucose (R_G values and co-pc)^{13,14} and 3,3',4'-tri-O-methylellagic acid (m.m.p. and co-tlc). This confirmed the 1 \rightarrow 4 inter-sugar linkage. The periodate